

CAIRT-PerReC

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Requirement Consolidation (PerReC)
Activity

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CAIRT measurement requirements assessment

Technical note on cloud influence

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<p>The statistics of the appearance of clouds in CAIRT limb views is investigated by applying raypath modelling through global high-resolution cloud fields.</p>		
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1. Introduction

The statistics of the appearance of clouds in CAIRT limb views is investigated by applying raypath modelling through global high-resolution cloud fields.

2. Methods

1.1 Limb-raypath modelling

Limb-raypaths have been precalculated using the following baseline:

- Observer altitude: 800 km
- Orbit: same as METOP-B
- Simulation time: 5 days
- Tangent altitude range: 2-21 km
- Number of horizontal across-track views: 16
- Horizontal distance of across-track views: 25 km
- Along-track distance: 50 km
- Vertical distance of tangent points: 1 km
- Length of single limb-path segments: 1 km

This amounts in total to 17 632 000 limb viewing raypaths (tangent points).

With on average 720 points along a limb-viewing raypath, the total amount of latitude/longitude/altitude points along all raypaths is 12 695 040 000.

Figure 1 shows an example of one segment of the calculated raypaths.

Figure 1 Example from the limb raypath dataset used in the study.

1.2 Cloud-cover fields

Global fields of cloud-cover where available from the PHILEA HALO campaign in summer 2023 from ICON-ART simulations based on analysis data from the DWD (German Weather Service).

- Available months: Mai-October 2023
- Used days in each month: 1st, 10th, 20th

- Horizontal resolution of cloud-cover in each file: 0.2x0.2 deg lon x lat
- Vertical resolution: about 1 km
- Time resolution: 3 h

An example of such a field of cloud-cover at 10 km altitude is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Example for cloud-cover dataset.

1.3 Cloud-cover along limb-paths

The meteorological fields of cloud-cover are interpolated (using nearest neighbor interpolation) in latitude, longitude, and time-of-the-day to each 1-km segment of all the limb raypaths described above. I.e. each daily meteorological field is sampled with the limb raypaths from 5 days. The example for one limb-view is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Example of the combination of limb ray-paths and cloud-cover.

1.4 Global statistics

Along each limb ray-path the statistics of cloud-cover is calculated (i.e. the ensemble are all the 1-km parts along each path): the maximum cloud-cover value, the mean and the standard deviation. Figure 4 shows an example of the maximum cloud cover value encountered by limb-paths with tangent altitude of 12 km.

Figure 4 Maximum encountered cloud-fraction along limb ray-paths with tangent altitude of around 12 km

3. Results

To produce global summary statistics, we counted as cloud-free only those limb-paths with no cloud-cover at all (i.e. maximum cloud cover for all 1-km path segments is =0%). This is considered as the most conservative approach. Results are shown in Figure 5 - Figure 7.

Figure 5 Global relative limb cloud cover within boxes of 10 deg latitude and 20 deg longitude for limb-paths with tangent altitudes provided in the title of each panel.

Figure 6 Same Figure 5 as but for zonal averages.

Figure 7 Absolute number of limb-views per day reaching down to the related tangent altitude without cloud interference.